

METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS MATHEMATICS OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the connection between Grade 9 students' metacognitive awareness and attitudes toward mathematics at Apyao National High School located at Quemtras, Quezon, Bukidnon, Philippines. It aimed to determine the level of metacognitive awareness, assess the students' attitudes toward mathematics, and explore the correlation between metacognitive awareness with students' attitudes toward mathematics. A quantitative research design was employed using a descriptive-correlational survey, and it was carried out on 30 respondents. A Metacognitive Awareness Test and an Attitude Towards Mathematics Test were adopted and utilized to gather the data. The analysis will involve statistical techniques such as Pearson product-moment correlation to determine the significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards mathematics. The results showed that the level of students' metacognitive awareness is moderately high. Moreover, it was revealed that the students' attitudes towards mathematics are moderately positive. Finally, the results indicated that there is no significant relationship between students' metacognitive awareness and their attitudes toward mathematics, and the Pearson correlation coefficient value is -0.173. This implies that there is a weak negative correlation between students' metacognitive awareness and students' metacognitive awareness and students' attitudes towards mathematics.

Keywords: *metacognitive awareness, attitude towards mathematics, high school students, descriptive-correlational*

INTRODUCTION

Many junior high school students often struggle with mathematics due to gaps in foundational skills, computational errors, and difficulty applying abstract concepts, leading to frustration, negative attitude, and decreased confidence. Despite the recognized importance of mathematics in equipping students with essential skills for future academic and career success, many students experience negative attitudes rooted in anxiety and low self-confidence, which are often exacerbated by insufficient metacognitive awareness (Dela Cruz & Muegna, 2024). The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) have highlighted significant gaps in Filipino students' mathematics proficiency, with only 16% achieving basic competency in PISA 2022 and the Philippines ranking last in TIMSS 2019. These challenges emphasize the importance of fostering metacognitive awareness and positive attitudes toward mathematics to improve performance. However, research also reveals disparities in metacognitive regulation among students of varying skill levels, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to develop these cognitive strategies and enhance attitudes toward learning mathematics. When it comes to the National Achievement Test (NAT) as released by NRTRC and as cited by Tan and Cordova (2018), the Region MPS is just 48.92% which is significantly below 50% as required by the DepEd.

Metacognitive awareness is essential for students across all educational levels, from elementary to higher levels. It encompasses the ability to understand and regulate one's own thinking processes, which is crucial for effective learning (Panchu et al., 2017). Since students are continuously developing their understanding and forming assumptions about their learning experiences, their levels of metacognitive awareness can vary significantly (Panchu et al., 2017). Those with higher levels of metacognitive awareness tend to exhibit faster and more substantial academic improvement. This is particularly evident when theoretical and practical studies are conducted to identify and enhance the specific components that contribute to their growth (Masoodi, 2019). Flavell (in Schraw and Dennison, 1994; Surat et al., 2014) identifies three components of metacognitive knowledge: declarative knowledge, which relates to self-awareness or understanding one's own abilities; procedural knowledge, which is concerned with comprehension of tasks and activities; and conditional knowledge, which includes knowledge of learning strategies. However, metacognition can also be viewed through a different perspective that identifies different levels of metacognitive thinking to enhance knowledge, awareness, and intelligence, referred to as the eight pillars of the metacognition model (Drigas and Mitsea, 2020). These pillars promote cognitive processes that support the use of deep understanding, cognitive abilities, self-regulation, proper adaptation to societal needs, pattern recognition, practical skills, and even enhanced memorization (Drigas and Mitsea, 2020).

On the other hand, many students encounter challenges in learning mathematics due to a lack of interest and negative attitudes, as the subject is frequently viewed as challenging and complex. They called for interventions to address these challenges in junior high school students (Ganal & Guiab, 2014). The affective dimension of competencies, such

as emotional competence, plays a vital role in mathematics curriculum and should be integrated into teaching and learning processes. Evaluating students' attitudes toward mathematics is essential for enhancing academic performance and fostering achievement. Positive or negative feelings toward mathematics significantly influence students' interest and motivation in the subject, as highlighted by Feregrino et al. (2021). Mathematics Attitude, or one's perspective on mathematics, plays a crucial role in understanding mathematical learning. Students who hold a positive view of mathematics tend to achieve higher performance compared to those with a negative perspective (Duque & Tan, 2018; Turra et al., 2019). Those with a favorable perspective on the subject tend to achieve better results. Students who held a positive view of mathematics were more likely to excel in the subject. Consequently, fostering a positive attitude towards mathematics could enhance the mathematical abilities of students in the Philippines (Tudy, 2014). The researchers Han and Carpenter (2014) emphasized that attitudes toward mathematics are formed by cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. Ingram (2014) discussed the affective component of attitude, which influences engagement and is shaped by cognitive beliefs about mathematics.

Examining the relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitudes toward mathematics is essential for improving learning outcomes and fostering lifelong learning skills. Metacognitive awareness enables students to regulate their thinking, while a positive attitude toward mathematics enhances motivation and engagement. This study focuses on Grade 9 students at Apayao National High School to determine how these factors influence their understanding of mathematical ideas, to inform teaching strategies, and to improve mathematics education.

Research Questions

The study aimed to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of metacognitive awareness among Grade 9 students in mathematics? In terms of;
 - a. Declarative Knowledge;
 - b. Procedural Knowledge;
 - c. Conditional Knowledge;
 - d. Planning;
 - e. Comprehension;
 - f. Information Management;
 - g. Debugging; and
 - h. Evaluation.
2. What is the level of Grade 9 high school students' attitude towards mathematics? In terms of;
 - a. Value;
 - b. Self-confidence;
 - c. Motivation; and
 - d. Enjoyment.

3. Is there a significant relationship between students' metacognitive awareness and their attitudes towards mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine if there is a significant relationship between students' metacognitive awareness and attitude toward mathematics. The level of metacognitive awareness will be determined by finding the descriptive mean using a 52-item survey questionnaire inventory by Schraw and Dennison, 1994 and students' attitudes toward mathematics will be determined by finding the descriptive mean using a 40-item survey questionnaire by Martha Tapia 1996. By utilizing this, the study seeks to provide insights into how students' attitudes influence their metacognitive awareness in mathematics. The study was conducted at Apyao National High School, a public school which is located at Quemtras, Quezon, Bukidnon, Philippines. The respondents of the study are the Grade 9 students in their second grading period SY 2024-2025. Focused on one section estimated to have 30 students who voluntarily participated in the study. Students in this area have multiple intelligences and are interculturally diverse students. The researcher utilized an adopted version of the "Metacognitive Awareness Inventory," a 52-item questionnaire developed by Schraw and Dennison (1994). This questionnaire consists of 52 statements that cover various indicators: Knowledge about cognition which includes Declarative Knowledge, Procedural Knowledge, and Conditional Knowledge, as well as Regulation of Cognition which encompasses Planning, Comprehension, Monitoring, Information Management, Debugging, and Evaluation. Participants responded using the options Always, Often, Sometimes, Rarely, and Never. The tool demonstrated strong reliability, achieving a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.971.

The respondents' level of attitude towards mathematics was interpreted using the following scale:

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
5	4.21-5.00	Always
4	3.41-4.20	Often
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes
2	1.81-2.60	Rarely
1	1.0-1.80	Never

Furthermore, the researcher utilized and adopted another questionnaire called the "Attitude towards Mathematics Inventory," consisting of 40 items created by Martha Tapia (1996). This inventory includes 40 statements that represent indicators such as Value, Motivation, Self-confidence, and Enjoyment. The pilot testing was conducted with grade 10 students for item analysis and validity purposes. Item analysis and validity testing were conducted through a pilot study involving grade 10 students. The ATMI consists of 40 items, which respondents rated on a five-point scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree, and it also displayed strong reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.942.

The respondents' level of metacognitive awareness was interpreted using the following scale:

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
5	4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
4	3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>
3	2.61-3.40	<i>Neutral</i>
2	1.81-2.60	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
1	1.0-1.80	<i>Disagree</i>

The study examined the relationship between students' metacognitive awareness and attitude towards mathematics, several statistical techniques were employed. The researcher employed a descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing quantitative methods to identify potential connections between these variables. Data will be collected using the metacognitive awareness inventory (MAI) and attitude towards mathematics inventory (ATMI). To determine the level of each variable, the researcher gets the mean and standard deviation of both metacognitive awareness and attitude towards mathematics. The analysis will involve statistical techniques such as Pearson product-moment correlation to determine the significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards mathematics. The researcher sent a written request to the Assistant Principal of Apyao National High School asking permission to conduct the research on the grade 9 high school students enrolled for the academic year 2024-2025 at Quemtras, Quezon, Bukidnon. The researcher ensured to give the informed consent form to the students asking their permission to participate in the study voluntarily. First, the researcher conducted a pilot test with grade 10 students to ensure the reliability of the survey questionnaires. After the result of item analysis, the researcher conducted the study by letting the grade 9 high school students answer the survey questionnaires of the metacognitive awareness inventory and the attitude towards mathematics inventory.

RESULTS

A. Metacognitive Awareness of Students

The first research question was to determine the level of metacognitive awareness of students in Mathematics. It was measured using a 52-item survey questionnaire inventory by Schraw and Dennison (1994).

Table 1. Students Metacognitive Awareness

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating	Items	Qualitative Interpretation
Metacognitive Knowledge	3.40	1.09	Sometimes		Average Metacognitive Awareness

Declarative Knowledge	3.38	1.08	Sometimes	5, 10, 12, 16, 17, 20, 32, 46	Average Metacognitive Awareness
Procedural Knowledge	3.35	1.05	Sometimes	3, 14, 27, 33	Average Metacognitive Awareness
Conditional Knowledge	3.48	1.13	Often	15, 18, 26, 29, 35	High Metacognitive Awareness
Metacognitive Regulation	3.50	1.05	Often		High Metacognitive Awareness
Planning	3.62	1.07	Often	4, 6, 8, 22, 23, 42, 45	High Metacognitive Awareness
Comprehension Monitoring	3.51	1.03	Often	1, 2, 11, 21, 28, 34, 49	High Metacognitive Awareness
Information Management	3.37	1.06	Sometimes	9, 13, 30, 31, 37, 39, 41, 43, 47, 48	Average Metacognitive Awareness
Debugging	3.42	1.14	Often	25, 40, 44, 51, 52	High Metacognitive Awareness
Evaluation	3.51	0.93	Often	7, 18, 24, 36, 38, 49	High Metacognitive Awareness
Overall Mean	3.46		Often		High Metacognitive Awareness

Legend:

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>
5	4.21-5.00	Always	Very High Metacognitive Awareness
4	3.41-4.20	Often	High Metacognitive Awareness
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes	Average Metacognitive Awareness
2	1.81-2.60	Rarely	Low Metacognitive Awareness
1	1.0-1.80	Never	Very Low Metacognitive Awareness

B. Students' Attitude towards Mathematics

The second research question was to determine the level of metacognitive skills of the students. It was measured using a 40-item adopted survey questionnaire inventory of Martha Tapia (2016).

Table 2. Students' Attitudes towards Mathematics

Subscale	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating	Items	Qualitative Interpretation
Value	3.93	0.73	Agree	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 35, 36, 39	PATM
Self-confidence	3.14	0.90	Neutral	9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 40	MPATM

Motivation	3.06	0.91	Agree	23, 28, 32, 33, 34	PATM
Enjoyment	3.47	0.94	Agree	3, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 37, 38	PATM
Overall Mean	3.40	0.87	Agree		PATM

Legend:

Rating	Scale	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive Attitude towards Mathematics (VPATM)
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	Positive Attitude towards Mathematics (PATM)
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral	Moderately Positive Attitude towards Mathematics (MPATM)
2	1.81-2.60	Strongly Disagree	Negative Attitude towards Mathematics (NATM)
1	1.0-1.80	Disagree	Very Negative Attitude towards Mathematics (VNATM)

C. Correlation between Students' Metacognitive Awareness and Attitude Towards Mathematics

The third research question was to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of conceptual understanding and students' metacognitive skills in mathematics.

Table 3. Correlation between Students' Metacognitive Awareness and Attitude towards Mathematics

Variables		Metacognitive awareness	Attitude towards Mathematics
Metacognitive Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	-.173**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.360
	N	30	30
Attitude towards Mathematics	Pearson Correlation	-.173**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.360	
	N	30	30

**correlation significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the results on the level of metacognitive awareness of students in mathematics, the overall mean of students' metacognitive awareness is "high". The study provides insights into students' metacognitive awareness through various indicators, including metacognitive knowledge and regulation. The overall mean score of 3.46 falls into the "Often" category, indicating a high level of metacognitive awareness among the students. The overall mean of the respondents' metacognitive knowledge was 3.40 ($SD = 1.09$), which is described as average metacognitive awareness. Specifically, declarative and procedural knowledge scored around 3.38 ($SD = 1.08$) and 3.35 ($SD = 1.05$),

respectively, has an average level of awareness, while conditional knowledge scored higher at 3.48 ($SD = 1.13$), indicating a high level of awareness. In terms of metacognitive regulation their overall mean is 3.50 ($SD = 1.05$), which belongs to high metacognitive awareness. While planning ($Mean = 3.62, SD = 1.07$), comprehension monitoring ($Mean = 3.51, SD = 1.03$), and evaluation ($Mean = 3.51, SD = 0.93$) all scored above 3.41, placing them in the "Often" category, which signifies high metacognitive awareness. However, information management scored 3.37 ($SD = 1.06$), indicating an average level of awareness. The result reveals of metacognitive awareness among students, with strengths in planning and comprehension monitoring but weaknesses in declarative and procedural knowledge. The result of the study revealed that students with higher metacognitive awareness tend to perform better academically and are more effective in managing their learning processes. Metacognitive training, through targeted interventions, can enhance metacognitive skills, leading to improved academic performance and better learning outcomes. The findings reveal that the high conditional knowledge scores align with research indicating that metacognitive strategies are more effectively applied when students understand the context in which they are used, underscoring the importance of contextual learning. The result is consistent with the findings of (Lestari & Jailani, 2018; Tak et al., 2023), students with a high degree of mathematical metacognition can analyze, manage, and regulate cognitive processes in mathematics reasoning.

Table 2 shows the results on the level of attitude towards mathematics, the overall students' attitude towards mathematics is "positive," with an average mean of 3.40 ($SD = 0.87$). It implies that the students have achieved a positive attitude towards mathematics. The study examined students' attitudes toward mathematics across several subscales. The results show that students generally have a positive attitude toward mathematics. Specifically, the subscales of Value ($Mean = 3.93, SD = 0.73$) and Enjoyment ($Mean = 3.47, SD = 0.94$), have all scored above 3.41, indicating a positive attitude, with the Value subscale scoring the highest at 3.93. The Self-confidence subscale scored 3.14 ($SD = 0.90$), and Motivation scored 3.06 ($SD = 0.91$), which is neutral, suggesting a moderately positive attitude. The result reveals that students hold positive attitudes towards mathematics in terms of value and enjoyment. However, their self-confidence and motivation in mathematics are neutral, indicating a need for improvement in this area. The high scores in value and enjoyment suggest that students appreciate the importance of mathematics and find it engaging, which are crucial for maintaining interest and motivation in learning. This implies that these findings are significant for educational practice. To enhance self-confidence, educational strategies should focus on building students' confidence through successful experiences and feedback. Curriculum development should emphasize real-world applications of mathematics to reinforce its value and enjoyment. Additionally, support mechanisms such as tutoring or peer mentoring could help students overcome challenges and build confidence in their mathematical abilities. The results are supported by existing literature that highlights the importance of positive attitudes toward mathematics for academic success. Kadirire (2017) found that students with positive attitudes toward mathematics tend to perform better and are more motivated to learn. Larkin (2019) also emphasized the role of self-confidence in mathematics, suggesting that supportive learning environments can

enhance self-confidence and lead to improved attitudes and performance. Furthermore, Al-Shammari et al. (2020) noted that real-world applications of mathematics can increase students' appreciation and enjoyment of the subject, aligning with the high value and enjoyment scores in this study. Additionally, Osborne et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of fostering positive attitudes towards mathematics through engaging educational practices, which supports the positive attitudes observed in this study. The result of this is also consistent with the study of Karjanto (2017), which examined the perspectives of 108 students studying mathematics at Nazarbayev University by utilizing the Attitudes Towards Mathematics Inventory (ATMI) developed by Tapia and Marsh (2004). The findings indicated that the students held a favorable attitude toward mathematics.

Table 3 shows that there is a weak negative relationship between the level of metacognitive awareness and attitude toward mathematics. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is -0.173 , where the p -value is $0.360 > 0.05$, indicating that the correlation coefficient was not statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. This meant that there was enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that there is no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude toward mathematics. This indicates that as metacognitive awareness increases, attitude towards mathematics tends to decrease. This suggests that students with higher metacognitive awareness might have a less positive attitude toward mathematics. This finding could indicate that students who are more aware of their learning processes might also be more critical or reflective about their experiences with mathematics, potentially leading to a less favorable attitude. The results were supported by the study of Sercenia (2021), which stressed the importance of metacognitive awareness and motivational beliefs in mathematics performance, indicating that metacognitive awareness indirectly influences performance through motivational factors. Hattie and Timperley (2019) discussed how metacognitive strategies can influence students' perceptions of their learning experiences, potentially affecting their attitudes. Students with higher metacognitive awareness are typically better at identifying their learning needs and adjusting their strategies accordingly. However, if students hold negative attitudes toward mathematics, they may be less likely to engage in these metacognitive practices, resulting in a weak negative correlation (Ajisuksmo and Saputri, 2017).

Conclusions

The researcher concluded that metacognitive awareness and positive attitudes are crucial for Grade 9 students' success in mathematics. Students who understand their own thinking processes (metacognition) can learn more effectively, approach problem-solving strategically, and monitor their progress. A positive attitude fuels motivation, perseverance, and a willingness to engage with mathematical challenges. Fostering these qualities can lead to improved academic performance, greater confidence in mathematical abilities, and a more profound appreciation for the subject's value. Therefore, educational interventions should prioritize developing both metacognitive awareness and positive attitudes toward mathematics in Grade 9 students. This study revealed a weak negative correlation between students' metacognitive awareness and

their attitude towards mathematics. This suggests that as metacognitive awareness increases, attitudes towards mathematics may slightly decrease, although the relationship is not strong. This finding indicates that other factors likely play a more significant role in shaping students' attitudes toward mathematics.

Recommendations

The study's conclusions lead to some recommendations for further research and action:

To foster enhanced metacognitive awareness and a positive attitude toward mathematics, educators should implement explicit instruction in metacognitive strategies such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating. This can be complemented by providing students with opportunities for reflection through journaling and self-assessment. Furthermore, cultivating a supportive learning environment that emphasizes effort, perseverance, collaboration, and achievement can build confidence and a sense of community, ultimately enhancing students' attitudes toward mathematics.

Promoting parental involvement is crucial for fostering metacognitive awareness and positive attitudes toward mathematics. This can be achieved by educating parents about the importance of these skills and providing them with resources to support their children's learning at home. Teachers can further enhance this by integrating metacognitive instruction into mathematics lessons, encouraging students to reflect on their problem-solving strategies and identify strengths and weaknesses, thereby developing a deeper understanding of their learning processes.

The weak negative correlation between metacognitive awareness and attitude toward mathematics suggests that other factors may significantly influence students' attitudes. These variables likely play a crucial role in shaping students' perceptions and engagement with mathematics, highlighting the need for further investigation into their impact.

Conducting longitudinal research provides a valuable method for exploring the development of metacognitive awareness and attitudes toward mathematics, providing educators with critical insights into how these factors develop and interact over time, enabling them to modify educational strategies more effectively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in strict adherence to ethical standards to ensure the integrity, confidentiality, and well-being of all participants. Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher obtained an Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) Permit from the institution, as well as the necessary permissions from the school principal and teachers. An explicit informed consent form was secured from all respondents, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights. Respondents were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity of the respondents was rigorously maintained throughout

the study. To safeguard data privacy, the researcher implemented strict measures, including the use of unique identifiers for respondents and secure data storage methods to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure of personal information. The well-being of the respondents was prioritized at all stages of the research, ensuring that no harm or discomfort was caused. The researcher declares that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources of information were properly cited. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias, and the results were used solely for research purposes. This study was carried out with utmost respect for ethical principles, ensuring transparency, accountability, and the protection of participants' rights.

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